

ON CONTINUED FRACTIONS AND THE

SORGENFREY LINE

by

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Abstract. We define in this paper a modification of continued fractions such that its lexicographic order coincides with the linear order of real numbers. Using this representation, we obtain a new proof of the theorem which shows that the Sorgenfrey line is not totally paracompact.

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It is known that there exists an homeomorphism of the irrational numbers, with its linear order topology, onto $\mathbb{N}^{\mathbb{N}}$, with its product topology.

In this paper we answer the following problem: To define a non-trivial order-preserving homeomorphism of the irrational numbers onto some linearly ordered space.

Let $x \in (0,1)$ and let $[(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}]$ its continued fraction (since $a_0=0$ for all x , we omit the first partial quotient).

We have that, the set of all points of $(0,1)$ which are irrational and its continued fractions verify that $a_1=n$, is $(\frac{1}{n+1}, \frac{1}{n}] \cap (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, if we place these intervals throughout $\mathbb{R}$, its approach to 0 for the right side. Nevertheless, the set of all points of $(0,1)$ which are irrational and its continued fractions verify that $a_1=n$ and $a_2=m$ is $[\frac{m}{nm+1}, \frac{m+1}{n(m+1)+1}) \cap (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$. Then, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, if we place these intervals, all contained in $(\frac{1}{n+1}, \frac{1}{n}] \cap (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$, throughout $\mathbb{R}$, its approach to $\frac{1}{n}$ for the left side.

The cause of these "oscillations" (the half-open intervals are, alternately, closed for the right or the left side, the sequences formed by the extremes are, alternately, decreasing or increasing), is the algorithm for obtain the partial quotients. Thus we define a modification of continued fractions such that the sequence which represents a number $x \in (0,1)$ is formed by non-negative numbers and we introduce, in the algorithm, "ones" for obtain always half-open intervals in the same side.

The lexicographic order of this new representation coincides with the linear order of real numbers.

Finally, we use this representation for prove that the Sorgenfrey line is not totally paracompact (This result was proved

by J.M. O'Farrell (in [4], using another method) and it is an answer to a question of A. Lelek [Univ. Houston Math. Problem Book, Problem N°99].

Theorem 1. For each number $x \in [0,1)$ there exists a sequence $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $b_n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ (for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$) and

$$x = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_2 + \frac{1}{1 + \dots}}}}}$$

(we show in the proof the sense of this representation)

Moreover:

- 1) x is irrational if and only if, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ there is $n' > n$ such that $b_{n'} \neq 0$
- 2) x is rational if and only if, there exists $n(x) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n \geq n(x)$ we have $b_n = 0$ (then $x = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + \dots + \frac{1}{b_{n(x)} - 1}}}$)

if $b_{n(x)-1} \neq 0$; $x=0$ if and only if, $b_n=0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$).

Proof. It is totally analogous to the continued fraction algorithm.

If $x=0$, we define $b_n=0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$

If $x \in (0,1)$, let $b_1 = \left[\frac{1}{\frac{1}{x} - 1} \right] \geq 0$ (we write $[z]$ for the "integral part of z ", the largest integer which does not exceed z). If $\frac{1}{\frac{1}{x} - 1} - b_1 = 0$, then $x = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1}} \in \mathbb{Q}$ and we define $b_n = 0$ for all $n \geq 2$.

If $\frac{1}{\frac{1}{x} - 1} - b_1 \neq 0$, then $\frac{1}{\frac{1}{x} - 1} - b_1 = y_1^{-1}$, where $0 < y_1^{-1} < 1$; let $b_2 = \left[\frac{1}{y_1^{-1} - 1} \right] \geq 0$. If $\frac{1}{y_1^{-1} - 1} - b_2 = 0$, then $x = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_2}}}} \in \mathbb{Q}$ and we define

$b_n = 0$ for all $n \geq 3$.

If $\frac{1}{y_1-1} - b_2 \neq 0$, then $\frac{1}{y_1-1} - b_2 = y_2^{-1}$ where $0 < y_2^{-1} < 1$; let

$$b_3 = \left[\frac{1}{y_2-1} \right] \dots$$

If x is irrational, we have that $\frac{1}{y_n-1} - b_{n+1} \neq 0$ (for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$)

and we shall write

$$x = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_2 + \dots}}}}$$

(we shall show the sense of this representation).

Clearly x is rational if and only if, there exists a $n(x) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $b_n = 0$ for all $n \geq n(x)$.

Let $x \in [0, 1)$ and $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, where $b_n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the sequence obtained using the above algorithm. We define

$$R_1(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1}}, & \text{if } b_1 \neq 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } b_1 = 0 \end{cases}, \quad R_2(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + 1}}$$

and, for each $n > 1$

$$R_{2n-1}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + \dots + \frac{1}{b_n}}}, & \text{if } b_n \neq 0 \\ R_{2n-3}(x), & \text{if } b_n = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$R_{2n}(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + \dots + \frac{1}{b_{n-1} + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_n + 1}}}}}$$

We have that: $R_1(x) \leq \dots \leq R_{2n-1}(x) \leq \dots \leq x < \dots < R_{2n}(x) < \dots < R_2(x)$

Moreover, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $b_n \neq 0$ we have

$$x - R_{2n-1}(x) < R_{2n}(x) - R_{2n-1}(x) \leq \frac{1}{n+1} \quad \text{and}$$

$$R_{2n}(x) - x \leq R_{2n}(x) - R_{2n-1}(x) \leq \frac{1}{n+1}$$

And, if there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $b_n = 0$ for all $n \geq n_0$, then

$$R_{2n-1}(x) = x \quad \text{and} \quad R_{2n}(x) - x \leq \frac{1}{n+1} \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_0$$

Thus, in the natural topology on $\mathbb{R}$, the sequences $(R_{2n-1}(x))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$

and $(R_{2n}(x))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converge to x , and we write

$$x = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{b_1 + \frac{1}{1 + \dots}}}$$

Corollary. Let $x, y \in [0, 1)$ and let $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and $(b'_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ its representations in the sense of Theorem 1, then $x < y$ (where $<$ is the linear order of real numbers) if and only if, $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \prec (b'_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ (where $\prec$ is the lexicographic order of $(\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\})^{\mathbb{N}}$). Then, the map which assigns to every $x \in [0, 1)$ its representation in the sense of Theorem 1 is a homeomorphism of $[0, 1)$ onto $(\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\})^{\mathbb{N}}$ with the topology induced by its lexicographic order.

Proof. Clearly $x = y$ if and only if $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} = (b'_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. We suppose that $x < y$; as $x \neq y$ there exists a first element $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $b_{n_0} \neq b'_{n_0}$; if $b_{n_0} > b'_{n_0}$ we have that $b_{n_0} \geq b'_{n_0} + 1$ and $b_n = b'_n$ (for all $n < n_0$), then $R_{2n_0-1}(x) \geq R_{2n_0}(y)$ and $x > y$. Then, $b_{n_0} < b'_{n_0}$ (and $b_n = b'_n$ for all $n < n_0$), thus $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \prec (b'_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$.

Remark. The above Corollary shows that this new representation allows us to give an order-preserving homeomorphism of $[0, 1)$, with the topology induced by its linear order onto $(\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\})^{\mathbb{N}}$, with

the topology induced by its lexicographic order. This order-preserving homeomorphism is analogous to which there exists of the irrationals numbers of the set $(0,1)$, with the topology induced by its linear order, onto $\mathbb{N}^{\mathbb{N}}$, with the product topology.

Proposition 1. Let $x \in [0,1)$ and let $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ its representation in the sense of Theorem 1.

Then:

We have that $b_1 = m$ if and only if, $x \in \left[\frac{m}{m+1}, \frac{m+1}{m+2} \right)$, and we have that $b_1 = m_1, \dots, b_{r+1} = m_{r+1}$ if and only if, $x \in [a_{m_{r+1}}, a_{m_{r+1}+1})$ and the sequence $\{a_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}} \subset [a, b) = \{y \in [0,1) \mid b_1 = m_1, \dots, b_r = m_r\}$ is strictly increasing and converges to b .

Proposition 2. Let $s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $I_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}, n)} = \{x \in [0,1) \mid x \text{ is irrational and its representation by continued fraction } [(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}] \text{ verifies that } a_i = s_i \text{ for all } i=1, \dots, 2r+1, \text{ and } a_{2r+2} = n\}$. Then, there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $b_1^*, \dots, b_m^* \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ such that $\overline{I}_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}, n)}^S = \{x \in [0,1) \mid x \text{ has a representation } (b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in the sense of Theorem 1 such that $b_k = b_k^*$ for all $k=1, \dots, m$, $b_{m+1} = n\}$ (where $\overline{I}_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}, n)}^S$ is the closure of $I_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}, n)}$ in the Sorgenfrey line).

Proof. In the fact, if x is irrational and its representation by continued fraction $[(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}]$ verifies that $a_i = s_i$ for all $i=1, \dots, 2r+1$ and $a_{2r+2} = n$ then x has a representation in the sense of Theorem 1 such that $b_i = 0$ ($i=1, \dots, s_1-1$), $b_{s_1} = s_2$, $b_i = 0$ ($i=s_1+1, \dots, s_1+s_3-1$), $b_{s_1+s_3} = s_4, \dots$
 $b_i = 0$ ($i=s_1+\dots+s_{2r-1}+1, \dots, s_1+\dots+s_{2r+1}-1$), $b_{s_1+\dots+s_{2r+1}} = n$.

Remark. We shall prove, using the representation obtained in Theorem 1, that the Sorgenfrey line is not totally paracompact (i.e. there exists an open basis for the Sorgenfrey line such that no subfamily of it which covers $\mathbb{R}$ is locally finite). This result is known (see [4]), but we shall prove it as an application of our representation.

Theorem 2. The Sorgenfrey line is not totally paracompact.

Proof. We shall construct an open basis $\mathcal{B}^*$ for $[0,1)$ (with the Sorgenfrey line's topology) such that no subfamily of $\mathcal{B}^*$ which covers $[0,1)$ is locally finite. (Cf. Theorem 1 in [2] and Theorem 2 in [1]).

Let $x \in [0,1)$ be a rational number, then there exists a sequence $(b_n^*)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ (with $b_n^* \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$) which is a representation for x in the sense of Theorem 1, and there is a first element $n(x) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $b_n^* = 0$ for all $n \geq n(x)$ (if $n(x) > 1$ we have that $b_{n(x)-1}^* \in \mathbb{N}$). For each $m \geq n(x)$, we define

$W_{R_{2m}}^x(x) = \{y \in [0,1) \mid y \text{ has a representation } (b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{ such that } b_n = b_n^* \text{ if } n < n(x), b_n = 0 \text{ if } n(x) \leq n \leq m, \text{ and } b_{m+1} \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\} \text{ is an even number}\}.$

Then, $\mathcal{B}^*(x) = \{W_{R_{2m}}^x(x) \mid m \geq n(x)\}$ is an open basis at the point x .

Let $x \in [0,1)$ be an irrational number and let $[(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}]$ its continued fraction. For every $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $(s_1, \dots, s_m) \in \mathbb{N}^m$ let $I(s_1, \dots, s_m) = \{y \in [0,1) \mid y \text{ is irrational and its representation by continued fraction verifies that } a_1 = s_1, \dots, a_m = s_m\}$. We have that

$$I(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}) = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} I(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}, n) \text{ where } I(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}) = [x_1, x_2) \cap (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}) \text{ (with } x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{Q}) \text{ and } I(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1}, n) =$$

$= [y_{n-1}, y_n) \cap (\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q})$ (with $y_{n-1}, y_n \in \mathbb{Q}$) for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, moreover $y_0 = x_1$ and $(y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a strictly increasing sequence which converges to x_2 . If $x \in I_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1})}$ we define

$$B^x_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1})} = \begin{cases} [x, y_{k(x)}) \cup [y_{k(x)+1}, y_{k(x)+2}) \cup \dots, & \text{if } k(x) \text{ is even} \\ \left[x, \frac{x+y_{k(x)}}{2} \right) \cup [y_{k(x)}, y_{k(x)+1}) \cup \dots, & \text{if } k(x) \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

(where $k(x)$ is the natural number such that $x \in [y_{k(x)-1}, y_{k(x)})$).

Then $\mathcal{B}^*(x) = \{B^x_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1})} \mid x \in I_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1})}\}$ is an open

basis at the point x .

Thus $\mathcal{B}^* = \bigcup_{x \in [0, 1)} \mathcal{B}^*(x)$ is an open basis for $[0, 1)$.

Let $\mathcal{V} \subset \mathcal{B}^*$ be a covering of $[0, 1)$ and we suppose that $\mathcal{V}$ is locally finite. Then there is

$$z_1 = \min([0, 1) \setminus \bigcup_{\substack{0 \in V \\ V \in \mathcal{V}}} V)$$

Since $z_1 \in [0, 1)$, there is some member of $\mathcal{V}$ which contains it.

From the construction of the $B^x_{(s_1, \dots, s_{2r+1})}$ it follows that any

member of $\bigcup_{\substack{x \in [0, 1) \\ x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}}} \mathcal{B}^*(x)$ does not contain z_1 . Then if $z_1 \in V \in \mathcal{V}$

we have that there is $x \in [0, 1) \cap \mathbb{Q}$ such that $V \in \mathcal{B}^*(x)$, and $0 < x \leq z_1$, thus $V \in \mathcal{B}^*(z_1)$. Let

$$z_2 = \min([0, 1) \setminus \bigcup_{\substack{0 \in V \\ V \in \mathcal{V}}} V \setminus \bigcup_{\substack{z_1 \in V \\ V \in \mathcal{V}}} V). \text{ Analogously to the above reason-}$$

ing, we have that if $z_2 \in V \in \mathcal{V}$, then $V \in \mathcal{B}^*(z_2)$. Let

$$z_3 = \min([0, 1) \setminus \bigcup_{\substack{0 \in V \\ V \in \mathcal{V}}} V \setminus \bigcup_{\substack{z_1 \in V \\ V \in \mathcal{V}}} V \setminus \bigcup_{\substack{z_2 \in V \\ V \in \mathcal{V}}} V). \text{ We can continue}$$

this construction and we obtain a sequence $\{z_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}} \subset [0,1)$ (such that $z_0=0$), and a sequence of half-open intervals $[c_k, d_k)$ contained in $[0,1)$ (for all $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$) such that for every $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $[c_k, d_k)$ is not covered by $\{V \in \mathcal{V} \mid \text{there is } z_{k'} \in V \text{ for some } k' \leq k\}$, but $d_k \in \bigcup_{\substack{z_k \in V \\ V \in \mathcal{V}}} V$, and $[c_k, d_k) \supset [c_{k+1}, d_{k+1})$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$.

The sequence $\{d_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}}$ converges to a point $x^* \in [0,1)$ in the Sorgenfrey line's topology, and x^* is not covered by $\{V \in \mathcal{V} \mid \text{there is } z_k \in V, \text{ for some } k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}\}$.

Finally, there exists $V_0 \in \mathcal{V}$ such that $x^* \in V_0$, then there is $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, for all $k \geq k_0$ we have $y_k \in V_0$. For every $k \geq k_0$, let $V_k \in \mathcal{V}$ such that $z_k \in V_k$ and $y_k \in V_k$; thus $V_k \cap V_0 \neq \emptyset$ for each $k \geq k_0$. Hence V_0 meets infinitely many members of $\mathcal{V}$, and this is a contradiction.

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